

Adsorption and Interaction of 1,2-Dibromo-3-chloropropane : Part II—with Illites

J. P. SINGHAL & C. P. SINGH

Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Muslim University, Aligarh.

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The adsorption and interaction of nemagon with acid and base saturated illites has been examined with the help of adsorption isotherms, pH, electrical conductivity and x-ray diffraction. The results furnished adsorption isotherms whose Langmuir plot indicated chemisorption at different sites of the clay surface. The order of adsorption agreed with the partial molar free energy changes. Desorption indicated a strong bonding of the chemical to the clay surface. Electrical conductivity and pH observations provided a powerful clue to the mechanism of adsorption with formation of ion-dipole complexes.

X-ray data confirmed interaction at the edge site of illites.

THE adsorption and interaction of pesticides on clays is one of the most significant processes influencing their persistence, movement and efficacy in soils. The phenomenon leads to physico-chemical changes¹ including nutrient availability and susceptibility to microbial degradation in soils. Illite is an important clay mineral occurring in argillaceous sediments found on a large scale in the soils of India and other parts of the world. The mineral has been found to possess reactive sites at the edges, corners, interlayer and interlattice positions²⁻³. Nemagon or 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane is an organic chemical which is extensively used to control nematode⁴ and fungus diseases in soils. A variety of methods⁵⁻⁷ have been used to provide information on the mechanism of adsorption and interaction of organic chemicals by clays. To mention a few, these include adsorption isotherms, pH, electrical conductivity changes and X-ray diffraction analysis. The work reported here examines the mechanism of adsorption and interaction of 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane on acid and base saturated illites.

Experimental

The clay mineral used in these studies was obtained from Ward's Natural Science Establishment, Inc. The mineral was from Morris, Illinois and was a monomineralic standard of the Clay Mineral Standards Project No. 49 of the American Petroleum Institute. Less than 2 μ clay fraction was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation. The suspension was then converted into Na-clay by treatment with 2*N* NaCl and washing with distilled water till the conductivity of the suspensions became constant. Hydrogen clay suspension was prepared as per Aldrich and Buchanan's method⁸ and the Ca-clay as per the ion exchange technique. The clays were quickly used for the adsorption experiments. The concentration of all the clay suspensions varied from

2.30 to 2.58 g of clay per 100 ml of water. The CEC of the clay determined as per Ganguli's⁹ method was 40 meq/100 g of clay.

Adsorption experiments were done by placing 5.0 ml of the clay suspension in a number of glass-stoppered tubes and adding various concentrations of standard nemagon solution (2000 μ g/ml) and adjusting the mixture to a constant volume of 25 ml with distilled water. The tubes were shaken for 3 hr each day for three days at 33 $\pm$ 1 $^\circ$ to attain equilibrium. The mixtures were then centrifuged and the supernatant liquids refluxed with alcoholic KOH. The pesticide was estimated as halide as per Volhard's silver thiocyanate-ferric alum method¹⁰. All samples

Fig. 1 Adsorption of 1, 2-dibromo-3-chloropropane on acid and base saturated illites.

were run in duplicate. In all cases a clay blank was included. The adsorption of nemagon was obtained from the change in the concentration of the solution before and after contact with the clay. Adsorption isotherms were plotted between equilibrium concentration and mmoles of the pesticide

adsorbed per 100 g clay (Fig. 1). The pH and electrical conductivity values of the equilibrium suspension were also recorded in each case.

For the X-ray analysis less than 2 micron acid and base saturated suspensions of illite were placed on glass slides and allowed to dry to form a well oriented layer. Similar samples of H-illite-nemagon complex and Na- and Ca- illite-nemagon complexes (treated with 157.48 mg per g clay in case of H-clay and 155.04 and 173.91 mg per g clay in case of Na- and Ca- clay) were carefully dried and oriented on micro-glass slides. Glycerine treatment also was adopted in case of Na- illite-nemagon complex sample. X-ray diffractograms were recorded both with the air dry and heat treated (at 550° for 1 hr) samples on a Philips diffraction unit at a speed of 2 degrees 2θ per minute using filtered Cu K_α radiation. Basal spacings in Å are given vide Table 1.

TABLE 1—BASAL SPACINGS OF H-, Na-, Ca-, NEMAGON, GLYCERINE AND HEAT TREATED SAMPLES OF ILLITE.

Nature of illite	Basal spacings at 001° reflections in Å	Interlamellar separation in Å
H-treated, oven dry	9.93 M	—
H-clay-nemagon complex(I) at 23.51 moles per 100g clay.	10.04 S	0.11
H-clay-nemagon complex(II) at 11.65 moles per 100g clay.	10.04 S	0.11
H-clay-nemagon complex(I) at 550°C	9.93 W	—
Na-treated oven dry.	9.93 M	—
Na-clay-nemagon complex(I) at 43.43	10.16 S	0.23
Na-clay-nemagon complex(II) at 33.6 mmoles per 100g clay.	10.04 S	0.11
Na-clay-glycerine treated.	9.93 M	—
Na-clay-nemagon complex(I) treated with glycerine.	10.16 W	0.23
Na-clay-nemagon complex(I) at 550°C.	9.93 W	—
Ca-treated oven dry.	9.93 S	—
Ca-clay-nemagon complex(I) at 40.45 mmoles per 100 g clay.	10.04 W	0.11
Ca-clay nemagon complex(II) at 31.26 mmoles 100g clay.	10.04 W	0.11
Ca-clay-nemagon-complex(I) at 550°C	99.93 S	—

Letters in parenthesis in column II indicate intensities S = strong, M = medium, W = weak.

Results and Discussion

The results of adsorption of nemagon on acid and base saturated illite suspensions (2.30 to 2.58% wt/vol) in the equilibrium concentration range of 0 to 6.13 mmoles of the fumigant per litre are represented by isotherm given in Fig. 1 (curves 1-3). An examination of the isotherms revealed that they were similar to class 'H' isotherms as defined by Giles *et al.*¹¹. Three regions could be recognised in the isotherms : region of complete adsorption, gradual rise, and a downward trend resulting in negative adsorption, in all the acid and base saturated systems. Initially the nematocide had such a high affinity for

the acid and base saturated illites that it was completely adsorbed till a critical quantity was reached (6.64, 13.11 and 14.72 mmoles per 100 g of H-, Na- and Ca- illite respectively). Such initial steep rises in adsorption were indicative of chemisorption occurring on the outer edges of clays with edge to edge ion attraction. Thereafter a change of slope occurred in the curves, the adsorption continued to increase till a value of 27.6 mmoles per 100 g of H-illite, 43.4 mmoles of Na-illite and 40.4 mmoles of Ca-illite was reached. The 'H' shaped nature of adsorption isotherms suggested adsorption occurring at different spots with two different energy levels on the illite surfaces as they underwent saturation one after another. The adsorption then declined. Negative adsorption of the fumigant appeared to be due to a change in the hydrophilic nature of the systems resulting in competitive adsorption of the solvent (H₂O) and release of the nematocide. Such effects have been reported by other workers also^{13,14}.

An attempt was made to fit the data into the Langmuir equation.

$$\frac{C}{x/m} = \frac{1}{KB} + \frac{C}{B}$$

where C was the equilibrium concentration of nemagon, x/m the amount of nemagon adsorbed, K and B

the constants. A plot of $\frac{C}{x/m}$ against C showed

small curvatures (Fig. 2). The plotted data showed at least two distinct linear portions signifying two different mechanisms or regions for nemagon chemisorption¹⁵ on illites. Since adsorption was well within the CEC limits, adsorption occurring in monomolecular layers by two different mechanisms appeared to be the main explanation to account for the above behaviour.

Fig. 2 Nemagon adsorption data for illites plotted according to the Langmuir isotherm.

Nemagon showed the maximum affinity for Na-illite and the minimum for H-illite, the adsorption followed the order Na-clay > Ca-clay > H-clay. The nature of the exchangeable cation thus determined the extent of adsorption and was in accordance with the deflocculation effects and surface area of Na-

Ca- and H- illites. The order of adsorption found further confirmation from the partial molar free energy changes that occurred during the interaction.

The changes in partial molar free energy $\bar{F}$ were calculated from the thermodynamic relationship

$$-\bar{F} = RT \ln \frac{C_e}{C_0} ,$$

where C_e and C_0 were the equilibrium and initial concentration of the suspension respectively. An

average of four values of $\bar{F}$ in case of H-, Na- and Ca- saturated illites were 304.2, 615.8 and 446.8 cal/mole respectively. This magnitude of the partial molar free energy changes indicated that the adsorption followed the same order as indicated by the adsorption isotherms.

Attempts to desorb nemagon from the acid and base saturated illites with potassium salts and repeated washings with deionised water did not prove successful suggesting that the fumigant was strongly bound to the clay surfaces by electrostatic forces.

A careful record of the pH changes observed during adsorption did not reveal any variation (pH 7.0). There was no change in electrical conductivity in the case of adsorption on Na- and Ca- illites (E.C. order 4.38×10^{-5} mhos cm^{-1}) though during the interaction of nemagon with H-illite it underwent a fall from 6.58 to 2.85×10^{-5} mhos cm^{-1} . These observations were highly significant and provided a powerful clue as to the mechanism of adsorption of the pesticide on the illites.

The structure of the nematocide could be represented as follows :

which showed it to be a dipolar and non-ionic molecule. Constancy of pH during its interaction with illites and non-variation of electrical conductivity in case of Na- illite ruled out any kind of protonation or ion exchange during chemisorption. The non-ionic character of the molecule with its tightly bonded nature and incapability of resonance also ruled out any possibility of formation of charge transfer complexes between these clays and nemagon.

The ionic nature of the clay and the dipolar character of the organic molecule may, however, result in a strong electrostatic attraction between the nematocide and the clay surface leading to the occurrence of an ion-dipole interaction with formation of ion-dipole bonds¹⁶ giving a complex of the type in case

of the base saturated systems ... (1)

To account for the fall in electrical conductivity in case of the interaction with H- illite the ion dipole complex formation can be represented as follows :

in case of the hydrogen saturated system ... (2)

The binding of the H^+ ion resulted in a decrease in electrical conductance. The saturation of the two types of sites one after another were in accordance with the earlier stipulations of two binding sites for adsorption with different energy levels.

An examination of X-ray data (vide Table 1) showed a small expansion in basal spacing viz., 0.23 and 0.11 Å on treatment of the Na-, Ca- and H- illites with nemagon. Heat treatment was generally without effect on the basal thickness of the complex. This showed only the adsorption of the chemical on the edges and corners of the clay lattice. The process of adsorption with the initial steep rise in adsorption isotherms thus appeared to be mainly the result of interaction of nemagon with the exchangeable cations and the negative spots at the edges, corners and or lateral surface of illites.

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